

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of the work environment and communication on work morale and its impact on employee performance

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Abstract

The goal of this study is to investigate how the work environment and communication impact work morale and subsequently influence employee performance. It is a quantitative research project that collected primary data from 75 employees at a branch of PT. GG Pasuruan, Indonesia, using a questionnaire. The data were analysed using SPSS Statistics version 22. The results show that communication significantly affects work morale, while the work environment does not. Both communication and the work environment have a significant impact on employee performance. Furthermore, work morale acts as a mediator in the relationship between the work environment, communication, and employee performance. This research aims to contribute to management and human resources literature by offering insights into the complex dynamics among these factors, providing a more relevant perspective on organizational success in today's business environment.

Keywords: Communication; Employee Performance; Organizational Success; Work Environment; Work Morale.

1. Introduction

In an era of business that continues to develop, factors that influence work morale greatly determine the success of an organization. High morale can create a positive work environment and motivate employees to provide their best performance. Two aspects that are considered to have a significant influence on work morale are the work environment and communication in the workplace.

The work environment is comprised of the physical, social, and psychological elements of the workplace, whilst information, ideas, and feedback are shared amongst members of the company through communication. A comfortable work environment and effective communication can be a catalyst for creating a positive spirit at work. These two factors not only influence employee well-being, but are also believed to contribute to improving individual and organizational performance as a whole.

Despite an abundance of information about how communication and the workplace affect workers' morale and productivity, there are several research gaps that require further attention. Some research may focus more on one aspect, without considering the complex interactions between the work environment and communication, and how these interactions impact morale.

In addition, there is still little research that specifically explores the key work environment factors that most influence work morale. Some research may be more descriptive in nature without providing an in-depth understanding of the mechanisms linking work environment, communication, morale, and employee performance.

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Additionally, most research tends to be general in nature and does not consider specific cultural contexts or industry sectors. Diversity in culture and work practices between organizations can result in significant differences in the way work environments and communications influence employee morale and performance.

An organization's most valuable resource for expansion and sustainability is its human capital. Therefore, further research into the intricate relationships that exist between the workplace, communication, morale, and employee performance can give managers and leaders deeper understanding that will enable them to develop policies that will boost employee morale and performance.

According to research by [1], a work environment that supports professional growth and employee empowerment can form a positive spirit at work. [2] research shows that open and transparent communication between colleagues and management can create a high sense of ownership and involvement. The research results of [3] concluded that compatibility between organizational values and the work environment can increase employee morale and performance. [4] research found that supportive communication and building relationships, strong interpersonal skills can stimulate enthusiasm and creativity. Recent research conducted by [5] shows that a work environment that prioritizes diversity and inclusion can create an inclusive and innovative spirit in the workplace.

Through this research, it is hoped that it can contribute to management and human resources literature by exploring the complex interactions between the work environment, communication, work morale and employee performance, as well as providing a more contextual and relevant view of organizational success in an ever-changing business era.

2. Literature Review

The study of the relationship between the work environment and employee morale has been a significant research focus. [1] research show that a work environment that supports professional growth and employee empowerment can form a positive work spirit. The fit between organizational values and the work environment has also been identified as an important factor in improving morale, as highlighted by [3] research. Communication between colleagues and management also plays an important role in forming work morale. According to [2], open and transparent communication can create a high sense of ownership and involvement among employees. [5] found that a work environment that prioritizes diversity and inclusion can create an inclusive and innovative work spirit. This study reveals that elements within the work environment, such as support for growth, organizational values, and communication, directly influence employee morale. Then the following hypothesis can be put forward: H1: Work environment influences work morale.

Previous research highlights a significant relationship between communication and employee morale. According to [5], communication that prioritizes diversity and inclusion can create an inclusive and innovative work spirit. Open and transparent communication between co-workers and management is also identified as a key factor in improving morale, as shown by [2] research. [4] study emphasizes that supportive communication and building strong interpersonal relationships can stimulate work enthusiasm and creativity. In this context, [3] found that a balance between organizational values and open communication can increase employee morale. The results of this research highlight the important role of communication in forming a positive work atmosphere, which ultimately influences employee morale. Then the following hypothesis can be put forward: H2: Communication influences work morale.

Research examining the correlation between the work environment and employee performance has become a significant research focus. [1] research show that a work environment that supports professional growth and employee empowerment can form a positive work spirit which ultimately contributes to better performance. Related research by [3] confirms that the compatibility between organizational values and the work environment can increase work morale which ultimately has an impact on employee performance. Certain aspects of the work environment, such as organizational culture and growth support, have been identified as key factors in improving individual performance. [6] demonstrate how improving employee growth and support inside the workplace may boost productivity and morale. Then the following hypothesis can be put forward: H3: Work environment influences employee performance.

Prior studies have demonstrated the robust correlation between employee performance and communication within organisational settings. As stated [5], communication that places emphasis on diversity and inclusion has the potential to foster an innovative and inclusive work environment, which in turn enhances individual performance. A strong sense of ownership and involvement can be created by managers and co-workers communicating openly and transparently, according to research [2], which is crucial for raising employee performance. [4] found that supportive communication and building strong interpersonal relationships can stimulate work enthusiasm and creativity, which ultimately has a positive impact on performance. Congruence between organizational values and effective communication was also

identified as a key factor in improving morale and performance, as found in research by [3]. The study's findings demonstrate the beneficial effects of effective communication on worker morale and output. Therefore, organizations can improve employee performance by prioritizing transparent, inclusive and supportive communication in the work environment. Then the following hypothesis can be put forward: H4: Communication influences employee performance.

Earlier research consistently affirms a positive association between work morale and employee performance. According to [5], high work morale can create an environment where employees feel motivated to give their best, which ultimately improves individual performance. [7] research concluded that high work morale can motivate employees to achieve their goals by providing sustainable intrinsic motivation. The research results of [1] show that positive work morale is closely related to increasing employee productivity and work quality. A recent study conducted by [8] also highlighted that high morale can strengthen employees' overall well-being, creating conditions that support improved performance. Thus, this literature confirms that high work morale is the key to improving employee performance. Factors such as job satisfaction, engagement, and intrinsic motivation are important elements that can be improved through human resource management strategies that focus on generating morale. Then the following hypothesis can be put forward: H5: Work Morale influences employee performance.

Employee morale is greatly influenced by the work environment, and morale ultimately affects individual performance. High work morale can be achieved in a workplace that fosters employee empowerment and professional development, according to studies [1]. Positive relationships among co-workers and possibilities for personal growth can be fostered in an atmosphere that can boost morale. [3] highlight that the congruence between organizational values and the work environment creates a climate that stimulates positive work morale. A motivating and supportive work environment can improve employees' psychological well-being, thereby providing an important boost to high work morale. In this context, increasing work morale then acts as a strong mediator in influencing employee performance. [7] research confirms that high work morale strengthens intrinsic motivation which has a positive impact on employee productivity and goal achievement. Then the following hypothesis can be put forward: H6: Work environment influences employee performance through work morale.

Effective communication plays an important role in shaping employee morale, which ultimately affects individual performance. Research by [5] confirms that communication that prioritizes inclusion and diversity can create strong work morale. Open and transparent communication between management and employees, as highlighted by [2], can build a high sense of trust and involvement. A study by [4] highlights that supportive communication and building strong interpersonal relationships can stimulate passion and creativity. Congruence between organizational values and effective communication was also identified as an important factor in increasing work morale, as found in research by [3]. Increased work morale then acts as a significant mediator in linking positive communication with employee performance. [8] research results show that open communication between management and employees can increase trust and well-being in the workplace, which ultimately contributes to improving individual performance. Then the following hypothesis can be put forward: H7: Communication influences employee performance through work morale.

Source: compiled by the author

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

3. Methodology

This research is a type of quantitative research. Using primary data obtained from respondents' answers to a questionnaire distributed to employees of one branch of the cigarette distribution company PT. GG Pasuruan, Indonesia. The total sample was 75 people.

This research consists of 4 variables that will be studied, namely the independent variable: work environment with 4 indicators (lighting in the workplace, temperature in the workplace, color management in the workplace, good work system) [9] and communication with 3 indicators (Not dominating the conversation, Creating a tense atmosphere, Listening to employees' opinions) [10], mediating variable: work morale with 4 indicators (Excitement or enthusiasm, Strength against frustration, Quality of survival, Team spirit) [11], and dependent variable: Employee Performance with 4 indicators (Quality of Work, Quantity of Work, Collaboration, Utilization of Time) [12].

The questionnaire was measured using 4 Likert scale criteria, namely: STS (strongly disagree) score 1, TS (disagree) score 2, S (agree) score 3, and SS (strongly agree) score 4. Data obtained from respondents' questionnaire answers were processed using the SPSS Statistics program.

4. Result

4.1. Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 Characteristic of Respondents

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	36	48.0%
Female	39	52.0%
Age (year)		
17-25	21	28.0%
26-35	38	50.7%
36-56	16	21.3%
Education background		
Senior High School	38	50.7%
Bachelor	21	28.0%
Others	16	21.3%

Source: processed field data

Table 1 above shows the characteristics of the respondents. The majority consists of 52.0% women, 50.7% aged between 26 – 35 years and 50.7% have a high school education.

4.2. Validity Test

Validity testing is done to assess how reliable the statements made in the questionnaire are. If the statements in the questionnaire can indicate what the questionnaire will measure and demonstrate the degree to which the intended measuring instrument is appropriate or suitable for usage, validity testing is conducted [13]. The SPSS software was used to process the data in order to do validation testing. The validity test results for each question item are as follows: Cronbach's Alpha > 0.60 for each statement item.

Table 2 Validity Test Result

Statement	r-count
X1.1	0.783
X1.2	0.594
X1.3	0.547
X1.4	0.573
X2.1	0.622
X2.2	0.458
X2.3	0.675
X2.4	0.876
X2.5	0.698
Z1	0.688
Z2	0.651
Z3	0.637
Z4	0.532
Y1	0.572
Y2	0.605
Y3	0.548
Y4	0.740

Source: processed field data

It is clear from table 2 above that every variable, which includes a total of 17 statement items, is valid. Each statement item's tabulated correlation value findings show a r-count that is higher than the r-table (0.254). The results of the validity test indicate that all statement items related to the variables are deemed valid and suitable for use as research instruments.

4.3. Reliability Test

The reliability test displays the consistency of an individual's responses to the statements on the questionnaire on a periodic basis in order to quantify the same symptoms. Every research variable is tested using the SPSS Statistics software in order to determine the degree of reliability of a statement. According to [13], The reliability test utilizes the Cronbach's Alpha method, where a variable is deemed reliable if its Cronbach's Alpha value exceeds 0.60. The reliability test results for the variables being studied are presented in the subsequent reliability test calculation table.

Table 3 Reliability Test Result

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Work environment	0.761
Communication	0.764
Work morale	0.736
Employee performance	0.758

Source: processed field data

The reason that all variables are deemed reliable is explained by Table 3, where the Cronbach's alpha value above the 0.6 requirement. According to the reliability test results, every variable is regarded as reliable and suitable for use as a research tool.

4.4. Classic assumption test

The classic assumption test is conducted as a preliminary step before performing the hypothesis test, outlining the criteria that must be satisfied before conducting the hypothesis test. These criteria include tests for normality, heteroscedasticity, and multicollinearity.

4.4.1. Normality Test

The normality test determines whether confounding factors (error items) are normal or not. As far as is known, these confounding factors are considered to be normally distributed. According to [13], the graph normality test can be misleading if it is not carried out carefully. This can mean that something looks visually normal but is not statistically normal, or vice versa, something looks visually abnormal but is statistically normal. As a result, statistical testing rather than pictorial tests is advised. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistical test is one of them. If the value of the K-S is greater than 0.05, the results are considered to not satisfy normal standards.

Table 4 Normality Test Result

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		75
Normal Parameters	Mean	0.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.20822104
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.097
	Positive	0.055
	Negative	-0.097
Test Statistic		0.097
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.080

Source: processed field data

Table 4 above shows that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (asyp.sig. (2-tailed)) value is 0.80. When $\alpha = 0.80 > 0.05$ is present, the data are regularly distributed.

4.5. Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: processed field data

Figure 2 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

According to [14], heteroscedasticity shows that different regression models have different variables. Graphical analysis methods can be used to identify heteroscedasticity problems. This graphic plot method is used to demonstrate the forecasted value of the dependent variable along with its residual.

Given the lack of any pattern and the randomly distributed dots above and below the zero point on the Y axis, Figure 2 above suggests that heteroscedasticity is not present.

4.6. Multicollinearity Test

Apart from that, the multicollinearity test explains that the multicollinearity test must also be carried out before testing the hypothesis. According to [15], the default tolerance value must be greater than 0.10 while the VIF value must be smaller than 10.00.

Table 5 Multicollinearity Test Result

Coefficients								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.268	1.500		1.512	0.135		
	Work Environment	0.361	0.089	0.394	4.073	0.000	0.856	1.168
	Communication	0.217	0.086	0.277	3.512	0.001	0.660	1.515
	Work Morale	0.188	0.112	0.177	2.685	0.002	0.726	1.377
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance								

Source: processed field data

Table 5 above explains that the VIF value is $1.168 < 10.00$ and the tolerance value is $0.856 > 0.10$. Therefore, it can be concluded that these requirements are satisfied and hypothesis testing can proceed.

4.7. Path Analysis

Path analysis is an expanded version of the regression model utilized by researchers to examine the correlation matrix of the causal models under comparison. In this research it is shown as follows:

Table 6 Path Analysis-1 Result

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.774	1.367		4.955	0.000
	Work Environment	0.040	0.093	0.046	1.424	0.673
	Communication	0.371	0.080	0.504	2.652	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Work Morale						

Source: processed field data

The results of the path analysis -1 from table 6 above are as follows:

- Influence of Work Environment (X1) on Work Morale (Z)

According to the data analysis above, the Work Environment variable's (X1) impact on Work Morale's (Z) has a significant value of 0.673, above the 5% significance level (0.05), these results offer insights into why the Work Morale variable (Z) is not significantly impacted by the Work Environment variable (X1).

- Influence of Communication (X2) on Work Morale (Z)

According to the data analysis presented earlier, the significance value for the impact of the Communication variable (X2) on Work Morale (Z) is 0.000, suggesting that it is significantly lower than the 5% significance level (0.05). These findings clarify why the Work Morale variable (Z) is significantly impacted by the Communication variable (X2).

Table 7 Path Analysis-2 Result

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.268	1.500		1.512	0.135
	Work Environment	0.361	0.089	0.394	4.073	0.000
	Communication	0.217	0.086	0.277	3.512	0.001
	Work Morale	0.188	0.112	0.177	2.685	0.002
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance						

Source: processed field data

The results of path analysis-2 from the table 7 above are as follows:

- Influence of Work Environment (X1) on Employee Performance (Y)

The analysis of the data indicates that the significance value for the influence of the workplace (X1) on employee performance (Y) is 0.000, which is below the 5% level of significance (0.05). These findings clarify the substantial impact of the Work Environment variable (X1) on Employee Performance (Y).

- Influence of Communication (X2) on Employee Performance (Y)

The relationship between communication (X2) and employee performance (Y) is associated with a significant value of 0.001, signifying that the significance level exceeds the 5% threshold (0.05), as per the aforementioned data analysis. These results elucidate the considerable impact of the communication element (X2) on employee performance (Y).

- Influence of Work Morale (Z) on Employee Performance (Y)

The data analysis presented above reveals that the correlation between Work Morale (Z) and Employee Performance (Y) is characterized by a significant value of 0.002, indicating a significance level below 0.05. These results provide an explanation for the significant impact of the work morale variable (Z) on employee performance (Y).

4.8. Coefficient of Determination Test (R²)

Table 8 Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	0.756	0.550	0.406	1.233	0.430	17.860	3	71	0.000	2.444

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Morale, Work Environment, Communication
 b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

As shown by the Adjusted R-Squared result, the goal of this test was to ascertain the extent to which the model could explain the combined (simultaneous) influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable [14].

The table above shows that the R square-adjusted value is 0.406, which means that the work environment, communication, and work morale variables account for 40.6% of the factors related to employee performance. Other variables that were not examined account for the remaining variables.

5. Discussion

The discussion in this research refers to the results of the analysis carried out on each hypothesis that has been tested. Based on the research results described previously, the explanation is as follows:

5.1. Work environment (X1) has no significant effect on Work Morale (Z)

This research shows that work environment variables (X1) do not have a significant influence on work morale (Z), in accordance with previous findings which also support the opinion that psychological and social factors can have a greater influence on work morale compared to work environment variables (X1). However, the analysis also revealed interesting preferences from respondents towards certain elements of the work environment and morale [1].

Previous research highlights the important influence of temperature on work performance and comfort [16]. The finding that the statement about workplace temperature received the highest score confirms the importance of this aspect in employees' perceptions of their work environment. On the other hand, statements about color management received the lowest scores, reflecting that this factor may be considered less relevant in a moral context.

In the context of work morale, research shows that team spirit has a significant impact on individual and group performance [17]. Therefore, the finding that team spirit received the highest score shows the importance of collaboration and support between colleagues in increasing work morale.

Thus, although there is no significant relationship between work environment and work morale, understanding individual preferences and values in work environment and work morale can provide valuable insights for the development of more effective management policies and practices.

5.2. Communication (X2) has a significant effect on Work Morale (Z)

This research reveals that the communication variable (X2) has a significant influence on work morale (Z), supporting previous findings which highlight the importance of effective communication in improving employee performance and welfare [18]. Analysis shows interesting preferences from respondents for certain communication and moral elements [5]; [3]; [4].

In the communication variable, the statement of not dominating the conversation received the highest score, indicating that the respondent valued an inclusive and supportive communication style. In contrast, the statement about creating a tense atmosphere received the lowest score, indicating that an atmosphere conducive to open and collaborative communication is more desired by respondents.

In the context of morale, the finding that quality through to the final product scored lowest may indicate that employees want a consistent and ongoing focus on quality in their work. On the other hand, team spirit received the highest score, which underscores the importance of support and collaboration between team members in improving overall morale and performance.

This combination of findings illustrates the importance of open, inclusive, and supportive communication in creating a work environment that strengthens employee morale. By understanding individual preferences and values in communication and morale, management can develop more effective communication strategies to improve overall employee performance and satisfaction.

5.3. Work Environment (X1) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y)

According to prior research that emphasises the connection between a positive work environment and improved performance, these results indicate a significant influence of the work environment variable (X1) on employee performance (Y)[19]. The analysis also illustrates the varied preferences of respondents regarding various aspects of the work environment and employee performance [1]; [3].

In the work environment variable, the highest score was obtained for the statement regarding temperature in the workplace, this shows that a comfortable temperature in the work environment is considered important by respondents. On the other hand, color management in the workplace received the lowest score, which may indicate that this aspect is considered less relevant or insignificant in determining employee performance.

In the context of employee performance, the finding that work quality received the lowest score may indicate that respondents consider the quality of work output to be something that requires improvement or further attention. Meanwhile, the time utilization statement received the highest score, indicating that time efficiency is considered important in assessing employee performance by respondents.

By paying attention to individual preferences and values in the work environment and employee performance, management can identify areas that need to be improved or corrected to improve overall employee performance and satisfaction. A better work environment management strategy can bring positive benefits in increasing employee productivity and well-being, as well as creating a better work environment overall [20].

5.4. Communication (X2) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y)

This research shows that the communication variable (X2) has a significant influence on employee performance (Y), in accordance with previous findings which highlight the important role of effective communication in improving individual and group performance in an organizational context [21]. The analysis also illustrates respondents' preferences for certain elements in employee communication and performance [5]; [2]; [3];[4].

In the communication variable, the highest score was obtained for the statement of not dominating the conversation, this shows that an inclusive and supportive communication approach was highly rated by respondents. In contrast, the statement about creating a tense atmosphere received the lowest score, indicating that an atmosphere conducive to open and collaborative communication is more desired by respondents.

In the context of employee performance, the finding that work quality received the lowest score may indicate that the quality of work results is something that needs further attention or improvement in an effort to improve performance. Meanwhile, the time utilization statement received the highest score, indicating that time efficiency is considered an important factor in assessing employee performance by respondents.

By understanding the importance of effective communication in the context of employee performance, management can develop more effective communication strategies to improve overall employee performance and satisfaction. This includes avoiding creating a tense atmosphere and encouraging open, collaborative and inclusive communication in the workplace [21]. Thus, investment in developing communication skills can provide significant results in improving individual and organizational performance as a whole.

5.5. Work Morale (Z) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y)

This research illustrates that work morale (Z) significantly affects employee performance (Y), aligning with prior studies that highlight the substantial positive influence of work morale on both individual and organizational performance [22]. The analysis also illustrates the varying preferences of respondents towards certain elements in employee morale and performance [5]; [7]; [1].

In the work morale variable, the highest score was obtained in the statement about team spirit, which shows that cooperation, support and a sense of belonging to a common goal are considered important factors in increasing work morale by respondents. On the other hand, the statement regarding quality up to the end of the product received the lowest score, this could indicate that respondents consider work quality to be something that needs to be improved or corrected in an effort to increase work morale.

In the context of employee performance, the finding that work quality received the lowest score may reflect that respondents consider the quality of work output to be something that requires further attention to improve performance. On the other hand, the statement regarding time utilization received the highest score, indicating that time efficiency is considered an important factor in assessing employee performance by respondents.

Through a better understanding of the important role morale plays in improving employee performance, management can develop strategies to build and maintain positive morale in the workplace. This can include efforts to strengthen team spirit, increase appreciation for work quality, and manage time more effectively [22]. Thus, investing in improving work morale can bring significant benefits in improving overall employee performance and satisfaction.

5.6. Work environment (X1) has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) through work morale (Z)

It is established that X1 has a direct impact of 0.046 on Z. Meanwhile, multiplying the beta values yields the indirect effect of X1 on Y through Z. Hence, the overall impact. The indirect impact value is bigger than the direct influence value, as indicated by the calculation results above, which give the direct influence value of 0.00814 and the indirect influence value of 4.07484. These findings demonstrate that X1 through Z has a major indirect impact on Y.

Research has highlighted the important role of morale in linking the work environment to employee performance. For example, research by [23]; [7] found that employee morale significantly mediates the relationship between work environment factors, such as supervisor support and development opportunities, and employee performance.

In this context, a work environment that influences employee morale, such as a positive work atmosphere, support from colleagues and management, as well as opportunities for personal growth and development, can lead to increased work morale. High morale can then move employees to work harder, be more dedicated and more focused, which ultimately improves their performance.

Therefore, by strengthening positive elements in the work environment that can increase work morale, organizations can indirectly improve employee performance. This shows the importance of understanding the mediating role of morale in linking the work environment with employee performance outcomes to design effective interventions in improving overall organizational performance.

5.7. Communication (X2) has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) through work morale (Z)

The direct effect of X2 on Z is known to be 0.504. In the meantime, X2's indirect effect on Y via Z is equal to the product of X2's beta value on Z and Z's beta value on Y, or $0.504 \times 0.177 = 0.040$. Thus, X2's overall impact on Y is equal to its direct and indirect effects, or $4.073 + 0.040 = 4.113$. The indirect influence value is bigger than the direct influence value, as indicated by the calculation results above, which give the direct influence value of 0.040 and the indirect influence value of 4.113. These findings demonstrate that X2 significantly influences Y indirectly through Z.

The study by [24]; [8] found that work morale acts as a mediator in the relationship between transformational communication, which includes communication that guides, motivates and inspires, and employee performance. These findings show that transformative communication can increase work morale, which then contributes to increased performance.

In this context, inclusive, clear and supportive communication in the workplace can increase employee morale. High morale can in turn encourage employees to work harder, be more dedicated and more focused, which ultimately improves their performance.

By understanding the mediating role of morale in the relationship between communication and employee performance, organizations can design more effective interventions to improve performance. This emphasizes the importance of developing a positive and supportive communication culture in the workplace as a strategy to improve overall employee performance.

5.7.1. Managerial Implication

Managers should focus on enhancing communication practices to boost work morale and subsequently improve employee performance. Creating an inclusive and supportive communication environment, avoiding tension, and emphasizing team spirit can lead to higher morale levels. Additionally, paying attention to factors like workplace temperature and time utilization can contribute to a positive work environment and ultimately enhance overall employee productivity and satisfaction.

6. Conclusion

This research highlights the finding that the work environment does not have a significant influence on work morale, while communication has a significant influence. Although the physical environment such as temperature and colour regulation in the workplace is considered important, psychological and social factors, such as team spirit and inclusive communication, play a greater role in influencing morale. A work environment that strengthens employee morale can indirectly improve employee performance through work morale, thus emphasizing the importance of understanding the role of work morale mediator in linking the work environment with employee performance. Likewise, transformative communication in the workplace can improve morale, which ultimately improves performance. By

understanding the mediating role of morale in the relationship between communication and employee performance, organizations can design more effective interventions to improve performance, with a focus on developing a positive and supportive communication culture. An emphasis on psychological and social factors in the work environment can bring significant benefits in improving overall employee well-being and performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Author wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

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